

1 **CoFe₂O₄ as a source of Co(II) ions for *in situ* oxidation of imidacloprid**
2 **insecticide using peroxymonosulfate: influence of process parameters**
3 **and solid surface changes**

4
5 Yoisel B. Broterson¹, Yeison Núñez-de la Rosa¹, Luis Guillermo Cuadrado Durango¹,
6 Moacir Rossi Forim¹, Peter Hammer², and José M. Aquino^{1,*}

7
8
9 ¹Federal University of São Carlos (UFSCar), Department of Chemistry, 13565-905,
10 São Carlos – SP, Brazil

11 ²São Paulo State University (UNESP), Institute of Chemistry, Department of Physical
12 Chemistry, 14800-900, Araraquara – SP, Brazil

13
14
15
16 * Corresponding Author. Phone: + 55 16 3351 8727

17 E-mail address: jmaquino@ufscar.br (José M. Aquino)

18

19

20 **Abstract**

21

22 Nanometric magnetic ferrite (CoFe_2O_4) synthesized by distinct methods was used for *in*
23 *situ* chemical activation of peroxymonosulfate (PMS) under neutral conditions to
24 oxidize imidacloprid (IMD) insecticide. The effect of CoFe_2O_4 load and PMS
25 concentration was investigated as well as the influence of phosphate buffer and Co(II)
26 ions. PMS activation by Co(II) ions, including those leached from CoFe_2O_4 , exhibited a
27 strong influence on IMD oxidation and, apparently, without substantial contributions
28 from the solid phase. Phosphate buffer had no significant influence on the IMD
29 oxidation rate and level, however, its concentration and solution pH have shown to be
30 important parameters, since higher PMS consumption was observed in the presence of
31 buffered solutions. IMD byproducts resulting from hydroxylation reactions and rupture
32 of the imidazolidine ring were detected by mass spectrometry. The CoFe_2O_4
33 nanoparticles exhibited an increase of the charge transfer resistance and an enhancement
34 of the surface hydroxylation after PMS activation, which led to radical (HO^\bullet and $\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$)
35 and nonradical species ($^1\text{O}_2$). The latter specie led to high levels of IMD oxidation even
36 in a complex water matrix, such as simulated municipal wastewater.

37

38 **Keywords:** Advanced oxidation process; Co(II) ion leaching; heterogeneous catalysis;
39 emerging contaminants; hydroxyl radicals; homogeneous process

40

41 **Abbreviations**

42

43 AsP – As-prepared samples without *in situ* chemical activation using oxidizer44 Cpt 400 °C/1 h – CoFe₂O₄ magnetic ferrite prepared by the co-precipitation method and

45 thermally treated at 400 °C for 1 h

46 Cpt 700 °C/1 h – CoFe₂O₄ magnetic ferrite prepared by the co-precipitation method and

47 thermally treated at 700 °C for 1 h

48 CMF: cobalt magnetic ferrite

49 DMPO - 5,5-dimethyl-1-pyrroline *N*-oxide

50 ESR - electron spin resonance

51 EI - electrochemical impedance

52 HRTEM – high-resolution transmission electron microscopy

53 HO• – hydroxyl radical

54 HPLC – high-performance liquid chromatography

55 ICP-OES – inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry

56 IMD – Imidacloprid insecticide

57 IMD fraction – $100 \times [\text{IMD}]_t / [\text{IMD}]_0$: [IMD] concentration at a specific time (*t*) and *t* = 058 ISCO – *in situ* chemical activation

59 MS/MS – tandem mass spectrometry

60 ¹O₂ – singlet oxygen

61 PDS – peroxydisulfate

62 PMS – peroxymonosulfate

63 SO₄•⁻ – sulfate radical64 SG 400 °C/1 h – CoFe₂O₄ magnetic ferrite prepared by the sol-gel method and thermally

65 treated at 400 °C for 1 h

66 SG700 °C/1 h – CoFe₂O₄ magnetic ferrite prepared by the sol-gel method and thermally

67 treated at 700 °C for 1 h

68 UHPLC-QToF MS – ultra-high performance liquid chromatography coupled to a time-

69 of-flight mass analyzer

70 Us – Assayed samples for the *in situ* chemical activation of PMS to oxidize IMD

71 XRD – X-ray diffraction

72 XPS – X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy

73

74 1. Introduction

75

76 Water contamination by innumerable anthropogenic sources [1–3], specially
77 persistent organic pollutants (POPs) [4], have emerged as one of the major challenges
78 facing our society. This scenario is aggravated by climate change [5] and a lack of
79 environmental investment by governments, which could jeopardize the United Nations
80 Sustainable Development Goals, particularly in developing countries [6].

81 To tackle this issue, the development and use of technologies to eliminate
82 organic pollutants is urgently needed [7–9]. For this purpose, advanced oxidation
83 processes (AOPs) represent an interesting option as they can produce highly oxidizing
84 radical [10] species, such as hydroxyl - HO• - and sulfate - SO₄•, mainly through
85 activation of peroxy-derived chemicals, such as hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂),
86 peroxydisulfate (PDS, S₂O₈²⁻), peroxymonosulfate (PMS, HSO₅⁻), among others [11–
87 13]. The *in situ* generation of radicals species can be mediated by UV radiation, electron
88 transfer reactions on selected anode materials, physical processes (electron beam,
89 ultrasound, or microwave), and catalytic/photocatalytic processes (Fenton and Fenton
90 like reactions) [14]. In the case of catalytic AOPs (cAOP), oxidants are activated by
91 electron transfer reactions with oxide compounds or metal ions, mainly derived from
92 transition metals [15].

93 Among the vast quantity of tested compounds for the *in situ* chemical activation
94 of oxidants, magnetic ferrite compounds have the advantage of being easily removed
95 from the reaction medium and exhibiting a strong interaction with metal ions [16,17]
96 that under optimized condition lead to high oxidation and mineralization levels of POPs.
97 Nevertheless, there is still a lack of understanding concerning the *i*) contribution of
98 leached metal ions (specially Co(II) ions) on the *in situ* chemical activation of oxidants
99 and their reactions with organic compounds and *ii*) temporal changes of the solid
100 catalyst to understand processes resulting in the material's inactivation. Regarding the
101 first point, Anipsitakis and Dionysiou [18] showed a fast (1 min) 2,4-dichlorophenol
102 oxidation by activated PMS using Co(II) ions (in the mg L⁻¹ range) in a buffered
103 phosphate medium. In contrast, several studies using CoFe₂O₄ magnetic ferrite (CMF)
104 reported a low contribution (in the µg L⁻¹ range) of leached Co(II) ions [19,20] to
105 oxidize POPs (see Table S1 for some selected papers). A significant effect of traces of
106 ions (µg L⁻¹), such as Cu²⁺, in the oxidation of POPs has been shown by Wang *et al.*, by

107 carefully controlling the medium with a buffered solution (pH 8 using tetraborate) [21].
108 The analysis of recent studies reveals that pH control is a key factor when activating
109 PMS to avoid changes on the oxidation performance of organic compounds as reported
110 in [22–24]. Concerning changes on the surface of solid catalysts, assessment of the time
111 evolution of surface sites can shed light on the mechanisms of PMS activation. Chen *et*
112 *al.* [17] observed that an increase of terminal oxygen species, *i.e.* surface hydroxyl
113 groups, were responsible for the high oxidation rates towards norfloxacin when using
114 $\text{Co}_{0.4}\text{Fe}_{2.6}\text{O}_4$. The variation of the relative amount of Co(II)/Co(III) and Fe(II)/Fe(III)
115 redox pairs and their binding energy on the catalyst surface can also activate PMS [23–
116 25].

117 In this context, the aim of the present work is to unravel the role of CoFe_2O_4
118 magnetic ferrite and Co(II) ions added to the reaction mixture in the *in situ* chemical
119 oxidation (ISCO) of imidacloprid insecticide using PMS. The use of CoFe_2O_4 and other
120 magnetic ferrites can lead to liberation of significant amounts of metallic ions into the
121 reaction mixture. However, since the catalytic effect of these species is frequently
122 misjudged, an in-depth investigation is needed to clarify this issue. So, the CoFe_2O_4
123 nanoparticles were synthesized by the sol-gel process (SG) and chemical co-
124 precipitation (Cpt) and the activation of PMS has been investigated with and without a
125 buffer solution at neutral conditions using different CoFe_2O_4 and PMS concentrations to
126 access the structural and electrochemical changes occurring during the catalytic process,
127 including the effect of the CMF synthesis procedure. All materials were characterized
128 concerning their morphology, crystalline structure, surface oxidation state, and
129 electrochemical parameters using high-resolution transmission electron microscopy
130 (HRTEM), X-ray diffraction, Fourier transform infra-red (FTIR), X-ray photoelectron
131 spectroscopy (XPS), and electrochemical measurements, before and after their use. The
132 main organic intermediates and working oxidants were identified using liquid
133 chromatography coupled to high-resolution mass spectrometry (UHPLC-QToF MS).
134 The results showed that the CoFe_2O_4 magnetic ferrite is a source of Co(II) ions to
135 activate PMS oxidant through the homogeneous process and so, should be measured
136 during experiments.

137

138 **2. Materials and methods**

139

140 *2.1 Chemical reagents*

141

142 The chemical reagents, including IMD (Imidacloprid, Milenia Agrociencias
143 S/A), $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (analytical grade reagent - a.r., Acros
144 Organics), NaOH (a.r., Panreac), Ethanol (absolute grade, Sigma Aldrich), PVA
145 (Polyvinylalcohol, a.r., available as Mowiol[®] 18-88, Sigma Aldrich), K_2HPO_4 (a.r.,
146 Sigma Aldrich), H_2SO_4 (a.r., Merck), $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (a.r., Synth), PMS (Potassium
147 peroxymonosulfate, a.r., available as Oxone[®], Sigma Aldrich), KI (a.r., Synth),
148 NaHCO_3 (a.r., Sigma Aldrich), isopropyl alcohol (99.8%, Panreac), t-butyl alcohol
149 (99.7%, Neon), furfuryl alcohol (a.r., Sigma Aldrich), L-histidine (a.r., Sigma Aldrich),
150 9,10-anthracenediyl-bis(methylene)dimalonic acid (ABDA: a.r., CaymanChem), DMPO
151 (5,5-dimethyl-1-pyrroline N-oxide, a.r., CaymanChem), HCOOH (a.r., J.T.Baker),
152 $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ (a.r. Synth), CH_3OH (HPLC grade, JTBaker) were used as received without
153 prior treatment. All solutions were prepared using deionized water (Millipore Milli-Q
154 Direct-Q[®] 5 UV system, $\rho \geq 18.2 \text{ M}\Omega \text{ cm}$).

155

156 2.2 Synthesis of CoFe_2O_4 magnetic ferrite (CMF) nanoparticles.

157

158 CoFe_2O_4 nanoparticles were synthesized by the SG and Cpt methods as reported
159 [26,27]. Briefly, in the first case, 0.5 g of polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) was dissolved in 100
160 mL of water at 90 °C, followed by the addition of precursor salts, $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.01
161 mol) and $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.02 mol). After complete water evaporation, the resulting
162 powder was collected and thermally treated in a muffle furnace (400 °C or 700 °C for 1
163 h at a heating rate of 20 °C min^{-1}) at air conditions. In the second case, the same amount
164 of the precursor salts was dissolved in absolute ethanol under magnetic stirring,
165 followed by the dropwise addition (32 mL) of a concentrated NaOH solution (3 mol L^{-1}).
166 The resulting mixture was kept under constant stirring for 30 min under ambient
167 conditions. Next, the resulting solid material was centrifuged and washed several times
168 with absolute ethanol and deionized water (until the washing water reached pH 7) and
169 finally dried at 60 °C for 24 h. After this step, heat treatment was carried out in a
170 muffle, as described above.

171

172 2.3 CMF characterization

173 X-ray diffraction (XRD) experiments were performed using a D8 Advanced
174 ECO instrument (Bruker) in the reflection mode ($\text{Cu-K}\alpha_1$ radiation of 1.54 Å, 40 kV,

175 and 25 mA) at a scanning rate of 1° min^{-1} from 5° to 90° (2θ). High-resolution
176 transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM) was used to analyze the particles' surface
177 morphology using TECNAI G² F20 (FEI) Instrument.

178 The surface analysis of CoFe₂O₄ (nominal composition) was carried out by XPS
179 using a commercial spectrometer K-alpha XPS (Thermo Scientific). The Al K α line ($h\nu$
180 = 1.486 eV) was used as the ionization source and the pass energy of the analyzer was
181 set to 50 eV for the high-resolution spectra. Other parameters kept constant were spot
182 size (300 μm), energy step size (0.10 eV), dwell time (50 ms), and number of scans
183 (10). The inelastic background of the C 1s, O 1s, Co 2p_{3/2} and Fe 2p_{3/2} high-resolution
184 spectra was subtracted using the Shirley method. The composition was determined by
185 the relative proportions of the peak areas corrected by the Scofield's atomic sensitivity
186 factors with an accuracy of $\pm 10\%$. The deconvolution of the experimental spectra was
187 performed using a Voigtian type function, with Gaussian (70%) and Lorentzian (30%)
188 combinations. The width at half height varied between 1.0 and 2.0 eV and the position
189 of the peaks was determined with an accuracy of ± 0.1 eV with respect to the
190 hydrocarbon peak located at 294.9 eV.

191 The surface functional groups were determined by using Fourier transform
192 infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) measurements. Samples were analyzed using the IR-
193 Prestige 21 spectrometer (Shimadzu), operating from 4200 to 240 cm^{-1} .

194 Inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES) was
195 carried out using a Thermo ICP OES iCAP 6000 (from Thermo Fischer Scientific). The
196 instrumental parameters optimized during analyses are described in Table S2.

197 Electrochemical impedance (EI: ± 10 mV perturbation, 5 kHz – 0.5 mHz) and
198 open circuit potential measurements (OCP in presence or absence of PMS and/or IMD)
199 were performed in 0.5 mol L⁻¹ Na₂SO₄ solution (at pH 7) at ambient conditions and
200 using a conventional three-electrode cell with a Pt foil and an Ag/AgCl (3 mol L⁻¹ KCl)
201 as a counter and reference electrode, respectively. The working electrode was composed
202 of a carbon paper substrate on which a slurry containing a mixture of CoFe₂O₄ (75%
203 *m/m*) was placed. The slurry was prepared at different treatment times using 20% *m/m*
204 Ketjen CB 600 (Nouryon) and 5% *m/m* polyvinylidene fluoride (Sigma Aldrich) was
205 deposited by drop coating and left at 60 °C for 12 h for solvent evaporation. The slurry
206 was previously mashed in an agate mortar and dispersed in 500 μL of N-methyl
207 pyrrolidone. All measurements were carried out in the dark.

208 The measurements were carried out for the as-prepared CMF samples (SG and
209 Cpt) and after 2 h of treatment. For this purpose, the catalyst samples were collected,
210 filtered, washed three times with deionized water, and dried under vacuum in a
211 desiccator for at least 12 h.

212

213 2.4 IMD oxidation and analysis of treated solutions

214 The *in situ* chemical activation of PMS using CMF for the oxidation of IMD (50
215 mg L⁻¹ – see chemical structure in Fig. S1) was carried out in a water jacket glass vessel
216 (400 mL) under constant stirring in the dark. Firstly, 150 mL of a buffered solution (10
217 mmol L⁻¹ de KH₂PO₄ at pH 7) was added to the reaction vessel followed by the solid
218 CMF. A neutral solution was chosen as previously reported [19,28]. Then, the system
219 was left under constant stirring for adsorption during 2 h. Immediately after that, solid
220 PMS was also added to start the oxidation reaction. The effect of different parameters
221 such as the CMF dosage (0.125, 0.250, 0.500 and 1.0 g L⁻¹), PMS concentration (250,
222 500, and 1000 μmol L⁻¹), synthesis method (SG and Cpt), and thermal treatment (400
223 °C and 700 °C) were studied. The solution pH was continuously monitored and
224 manually adjusted by adding concentrated/diluted H₂SO₄ or NaOH solutions. Other
225 operational variables, such as the treatment time, solution temperature, and stirring were
226 kept constant at 120 min, 25 °C, and 600 rpm, respectively. The samples were analyzed
227 after collecting them from the reaction mixture at predetermined time intervals, filtered
228 through a 0.22 μm cellulose acetate cartridge, and quenched with excess Na₂S₂O₃ (1.0
229 mol L⁻¹), except when residual oxidant was quantified. A recycling test (5 consecutive
230 degradation experiments) was also carried out after optimization of the above
231 conditions. For this purpose, after each run, the CMF catalyst was recovered by vacuum
232 filtration, washed thoroughly with deionized water, and dried under vacuum before
233 further use.

234 After initial optimization using deionized water, tap water and a simulated
235 municipal effluent wastewater (SMWW) were tested (see Table S3 and S4 and Text S1
236 for characterization and composition of such water matrices) to assess the influence of
237 common inorganic and organic interferences in real situations.

238 The evolution of the IMD concentration was monitored by high-performance
239 liquid chromatography (HPLC, Shimadzu 20A) at 270 nm using a core-shell C-18
240 reversed-phase column as the stationary phase (150 mm × 4.6 mm i.d., 5 μm particle
241 size, 100 Å pore size, from Phenomenex®). A mixture of aqueous 0.1% (V/V) formic

242 acid (eluent A) and methanol (eluent B) was used as the mobile phase in a gradient
243 elution mode (from 20% to 90% of B in 8 min and then, back to 20% after 2 min and
244 keeping this condition for 2 min before further analyses). The flow rate, injection
245 volume, and temperature of the column were kept fixed at 1.0 mL min^{-1} , $25 \text{ }\mu\text{L}$, and 24
246 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, respectively. When required, the amount of residual oxidant was determined using
247 the spectrophotometric method adapted from the work of Liang *et al.* [29].

248 Ultra-high performance liquid chromatography coupled to a time-of-flight mass
249 analyzer (UHPLC-QToF MS) was used in the optimized conditions to analyze
250 intermediates formed during the IMD oxidation process, according to a methodology
251 described in Text S2 and Table S5. UHPLC-QToF MS and ESR analyses were also
252 used to identify the main working oxidant species (mainly HO^{\bullet}) using a DMPO solution
253 as spin probe. Experimental details can be seen in Text S3, in the supplementary
254 material section.

255 Experiments in the presence of commonly known scavengers (0.1 mol L^{-1}), such
256 as isopropyl alcohol, tert-butyl alcohol, furfuryl alcohol, and L-histidine were used to
257 assess the effect of HO^{\bullet} and $\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$ radicals and $^1\text{O}_2$. To complement and get further
258 evidence on the role of $^1\text{O}_2$, PMS activation using CoFe_2O_4 and Co(II) in the presence
259 of ABDA [30] was carried out, as described in Text S4. ABDA was considered to be a
260 specific compound to react with $^1\text{O}_2$. Finally, the dissolved oxygen concentration was
261 measured using a Visiferm DO type sensor.

262 The chromatographic procedures to determine carboxylic acids and inorganic
263 ions can be seen in Text S5.

264

265 **3. Results and discussion**

266

267 *3.1 Characterization of the as-prepared CoFe_2O_4 magnetic ferrite (CMF)*

268 Fig. 1a shows TEM images of the as-prepared cobalt magnetic ferrite (CMF)
269 material synthesized by SG and Cpt methods. The morphology of the nanoparticles
270 exhibited a globular structure with many agglomerates for both synthesized conditions.
271 As expected, the mean particle size was about 10 nm and larger than 20 nm of samples
272 heat treated at $400 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $700 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, respectively – see Fig. S2 and Table S6 of histograms
273 and mean particle sizes, respectively. The SG $700 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}/1 \text{ h}$ compound showed unusually
274 larger size of 86 nm. The crystallinity of CMF nanoparticles was confirmed by HRTEM
275 micrographs, as shown in Fig. S3. The lattice fringe spacing was close to $4.7 \text{ }\text{\AA}$ (SG 700

276 °C/1 h, Cpt 400 °C/1 h, and Cpt 700 °C/1 h samples) and 2.9 Å (SG 400 °C/1 h),
277 corresponding to the (111) and (022) diffraction planes of CMF.

278 Fig. S4 shows the XRD of the as-prepared magnetic material and for distinct
279 synthesis and thermal treatment. The diffraction pattern of all tested materials can be
280 indexed to the ICSD card number 98-010-9045 of CoFe₂O₄. As expected, high
281 temperatures led to more defined diffraction peaks without impurities in the XRD
282 pattern.

283 FTIR spectra of the AsP magnetic compound are showed in Fig. S5. In general,
284 some common features can be noticed, *i.e.*, *i*) a weak band around 3500 cm⁻¹ (more
285 intense for the SG 400 °C/1 h sample) due to the O-H bond stretching, which can be
286 related by the surface terminations due to exposure to the environment (and consequent
287 adsorption of moisture) or, in the case of sol-gel synthesis, to traces of polyvinyl
288 alcohol; *ii*) O=C=O stretching vibrations due to atmospheric CO₂ at *ca.* 2350 cm⁻¹, *iii*)
289 C=O stretching *ca.* 1700 cm⁻¹, and *iv*) Fe-O and Co-O bond vibration bands at *ca.* 560
290 to *ca.* 400 cm⁻¹, respectively.

291 The surface composition and bonding states of the AsP CMF nanoparticles were
292 investigated by *ex situ* XPS measurements. As can be observed in Fig S6, the O 1s core-
293 level spectra were deconvoluted into four peaks. The main components of all spectra are
294 related to O-Metal (O⁻²) bonds at 530.0 eV, hydroxyl groups (HO-Metal) at 531.2 eV,
295 O-C and O-C=O type bonds of surface contamination (adventitious carbon) at about
296 532.0 and 533.0 eV, respectively [31]. The main difference among these spectra is the
297 higher contribution of oxygenated groups of adventitious carbon and higher intensity of
298 the O-H bonds due to traces of PVA observed for the SG 400 °C/1 h sample, in
299 agreement with infrared results. The Co 2p_{3/2} high-resolution spectra were deconvoluted
300 into five peaks, three of them shake-up satellites. The most intense components refer to
301 CoFe₂O₄ (and/or Co₃O₄) at 779.7 eV and Co(OH)₂ surface groups at 781.4 eV [31], as
302 showed in Fig. S7. Clearly, for samples prepared by the sol-gel method, the Co-OH
303 peak intensities are higher due to the PVA precursor. The Fe 2p_{3/2} spectra, shown in Fig.
304 S8, were fitted by four components and attributed to FeO at 709.5 eV, the most intense
305 to CoFe₂O₄ at 710.8 eV, and FeOOH at 712.3 eV. In general, all deconvoluted spectra
306 are similar, confirming the presence of the CoFe₂O₄ phase, except for the sol-gel
307 samples where trace of PVA were detected. Finally, as can be observed in Fig S9, the C
308 1s spectra were deconvoluted into four peaks related to hydrocarbons (C-H) at 284.9 eV
309 and oxygenated groups of alcohol/ether (C-O type at 286.3 eV), carbonyl (C=O at 287.7

310 eV, except for the Cpt samples), and carboxyl (-O-C=O at 289.4 eV) and mainly due to
311 carbon contamination of the surface and synthesis conditions.

312

313 3.2 Catalytic performance evaluation: heterogeneous vs. homogeneous processes

314 3.2.1 PMS activation by CoFe_2O_4 for IMD oxidation: effect of $[\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4]$ and $[\text{PMS}]$

315 Fig. 2 shows the evolution of the remaining fraction of IMD and PMS
316 consumption as a function of treatment time using $500 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ of PMS at pH 7. As
317 observed in Fig. 2a for the SG $400^\circ\text{C}/1 \text{ h}$ sample, there is a clear synergism between
318 CMF and PMS showing a fast IMD concentration decrease. This can be seen when
319 comparing the summation curve (dashed line in Fig. 2a) from experiments without
320 catalyst and PMS (0.125 g L^{-1} of CMF), being well above the curves when using a
321 mixture of catalyst and oxidant. Concerning the oxidation rate, no significant difference
322 of the IMD degradation curves was observed for CMF concentrations, tested in the
323 range of 0.125 to 1.00 g L^{-1} . All these points indicate that *i)* PMS is being activated to
324 produce HO^\bullet radical species (see discussion in section 3.3) and *ii)* low amounts of CMF
325 is sufficient for a complete IMD oxidation. The unexpected low PMS consumption
326 when using high amounts of CMF is due to its agglomeration in solution (Fig. 2b)
327 leading to a decrease of the available surface sites [32,33]. Consequently, 0.125 g L^{-1} of
328 CMF is enough to assure complete oxidation of IMD and total PMS consumption.

329 The evolution of the IMD fraction and PMS consumption as a function of time
330 when using distinct concentrations of PMS (from 0 to $1000 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$) and 0.125 g L^{-1} of
331 CMF at pH 7 can be seen in Fig. 3a. For PMS concentration values higher than 250
332 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$, complete oxidation of IMD is achieved after 30 min. In all tested conditions,
333 PMS is completely consumed within 60 min of experiment (see Fig. 3b); however, the
334 initial amount of PMS seems to be insufficient to completely oxidize IMD when using
335 $250 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ of PMS. Similar experiments were also carried out in the absence of the
336 CMF material to assess the influence of PMS to solely oxidize IMD. As can be seen in
337 Fig. S10, complete oxidation was only reached after 2 h of experiment when using 1000
338 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ of PMS. For lower concentrations, more than 6 h is required to oxidize IMD
339 (to *ca.* 90%).

340 After this initial optimization concerning the catalyst load (0.125 g L^{-1}) and
341 PMS concentration ($500 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$) at neutral conditions, new experiments were carried
342 out to compare the performance of the different synthesized materials, *i.e.*, SG 400
343 $^\circ\text{C}/1$, SG $700 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}/1 \text{ h}$, Cpt $400 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}/1 \text{ h}$, and Cpt $700 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}/1 \text{ h}$, as showed in Fig. 4. For all

344 prepared materials, the oxidation rate (close to 0.5 min^{-1}) and levels as well as the
345 oxidant consumption were similar and independently of the synthesis conditions and
346 particle size. This behavior was unexpected and may hint on some uncontrolled
347 variables, such as Co(II) ion leaching or even the use of buffered solution. In the latter
348 case, as showed in Fig S11a and Table S7, for a complete oxidation ($\sim 30 \text{ min}$) only a
349 small decrease of the IMD oxidation rate (0.53 min^{-1}) was observed when compared to
350 the condition without buffer (0.14 min^{-1}). As the amount of PMS was high enough, no
351 further deleterious effects on the oxidation rate and level of IMD was observed. In the
352 absence of buffer and with no pH control, IMD oxidation rate dropped one order of
353 magnitude (0.020 min^{-1}) with 90% oxidation in 120 min. In addition, a high
354 consumption of PMS is observed when phosphate buffer was used (see Fig. S11b). Such
355 behavior is due to the scavenging effect of H_2PO_4^- ions [34] on produced reactive
356 oxygen species. Undoubtedly, pH monitoring and control (see the pH evolution without
357 buffer in Fig. S11c) is of paramount importance as well as the use of buffer (type and
358 concentration [35]) and PMS concentration.

359 Considering Co(II) ion leaching, ICP-OES measurements were carried out as
360 showed in Table S8. In all experiments, shown in Fig. 4, Co and Fe ions were detected.
361 To verify a possible influence of these ions on IMD oxidation, a new experiment was
362 carried out concerning the addition of Co(II) and Fe(III) ions in the absence of the CMF
363 nanomaterial. As can be seen in Fig. 5, the use of 200 or $20 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ of Co(II) ions led to
364 a prompt oxidation of IMD in less than 30 min with almost complete PMS consumption
365 after 1 h and 2 h, respectively. This result was very similar to that when using the CMF
366 nanoparticles (see red square). On the other hand, the use of $50 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ of Fe(III) ions
367 led to 80% of IMD oxidation after 2 h with only 10% PMS consumption after 2 h. Other
368 experiments were carried out using decreasing amounts of Co(II) ions, as showed in
369 Fig. S12. For Co(II) ion concentration higher than $15.6 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, complete oxidation of
370 IMD was attained in less than 30 min, whereas 7.8 and $3.9 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ required *ca.* 1 h of
371 reaction. At this point and despite that some studies do not address the effect of PMS
372 activation upon Co(II) ion leaching (see Table S1), only a marginal influence is claimed
373 on Co(II) ions, *i.e.*, only a small contribution of homogeneous reaction. To fully address
374 this issue, experiments with Co(II) addition were performed without phosphate buffer
375 (with or without pH control by manual additions of diluted H_2SO_4 and/or NaOH
376 solutions). As seen in Fig. S13, no deleterious effect on IMD oxidation level or rate (see
377 Table S6) was observed for the homogeneous process in the presence or absence of

378 buffer if pH was kept at ~7. When solution pH was left varying in the absence of buffer
379 (Fig. S13c) a significant decrease of the IMD oxidation rate (one order of magnitude:
380 0.039 min^{-1}) and complete oxidation after 60 min was observed after the solution pH
381 dropped to 3 (after addition of PMS) and then remained constant during the entire
382 experiment. Once again, the key difference among tested conditions was the superior
383 PMS consumption (Fig. S13b) in the presence of phosphate buffer (~100% in
384 comparison to less than 40%) due to quenching promoted by H_2PO_4^- ions.

385 Based on results obtained in experiments with Co(II) ions and CMF material at
386 different conditions, the oxidation of IMD seems to be mediated by Co(II) ions leaching
387 from the magnetic ferrite particles. In fact, the solid material act as a Co(II) ion source,
388 which efficiently activates PMS if pH is kept under neutral conditions (pH 7).
389 Therefore, correction and monitoring of solution pH is highly recommended.

390 To tackle the issue of Co(II) leaching from CMF, two strategies were tempted
391 (see Text S5): *i*) carbonization of the CMF nanoparticles obtained by the Cpt method at
392 $700 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}/1 \text{ h}$ (no interferences from PVA) using glucose, and *ii*) carbonization of the
393 resulting products from the Sol-gel synthesis at $400 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (SG $400 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}/1 \text{ h @C}$) and $700 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
394 (SG $700 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}/1 \text{ h @C}$) for 1 h. Both strategies aimed to envelop CMF nanoparticles with
395 a carbon layer using a tube furnace at anoxic conditions (N_2 gas). As can be seen in Fig
396 S14 and S15, the oxidation rate and levels remained equal as those previously obtained
397 without carbonization, *i.e.*, the IMD molecule was promptly oxidized in less than 30
398 min. The only observed difference refers to the PMS consumption rate (see Fig. S15b).
399 The amount of Co and Fe ions detected in experiments of Fig. S14 and S15 is presented
400 in Table S9. In all analyzed conditions, Co and Fe ions were detected and at unexpected
401 high values particularly for the surface modification carried out using glucose. Low
402 values of Co and Fe ions were only observed for the SG $700 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}/1 \text{ h@C}$ samples, *i.e.*
403 tens of micrograms per liter. The detected quantities of Co ions explain the astonishing
404 high values of IMD oxidation rate and levels shown in Fig. S14 and S15. The reason for
405 that lies in the non-uniform carbon particle passivation allowing ion leaching, as shown
406 by the HRTEM images in Fig. S16.

407 Thus, for experiments with tap water and simulated municipal wastewater
408 (SMWW), the oxidation performance of IMD was evaluated using the CMF SG 700
409 $^\circ\text{C}/1 \text{ h@C}$ sample as heterogenous and Co(II) ($38 \text{ } \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$: the same value reported in
410 Table S9) as homogenous catalyst.

411

412 3.2.2 PMS activation by modified CoFe_2O_4 and Co(II) ions for IMD oxidation in a
413 SMWW and tap water

414 The activation of oxidants in real water matrices is challenging due to the
415 scavenging effect promoted by inorganic ions (such as HCO_3^- , CO_3^{2-} , Cl^- , etc.) and
416 organic matter, such as humic acid. SMWW and tap water matrices, detailed in Table
417 S3 and S4 and Text S1, were used to assess the oxidation performance of the SG 700
418 °C/1 h@C sample towards the IMD insecticide. To compare this process with the *in situ*
419 chemical activation of PMS using dissolved Co(II) ions, same experiments were carried
420 out using $38 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ of Co(II) ions. As can be seen in Fig. S17, the use of SG 700 °C/1
421 h@C and Co(II) ions led after 120 min to 70% and 85% IMD oxidation in SMWW,
422 respectively. As expected, the oxidation rate (*ca.* $2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$ for SG 700 °C/1 h@C
423 and Co(II) ions) in the simulated effluent decreased due to the presence of inorganic and
424 organic species that consumed the generated HO^\bullet radical species. The latter behavior is
425 significant and might indicate different oxidizing species [10], such as $^1\text{O}_2$, rather than
426 HO^\bullet and/or $\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$ (see discussion below). The distinct oxidation levels of IMD
427 achieved for Co(II) ions and solid CMF might be due to complete PMS consumption.
428 As expected, in the experiments using tap water (Fig. S18), the oxidation rate was
429 higher than when using SMWW due to lower content of inorganic ions and dissolved
430 organic matter. Compared to experiments with ultrapure H_2O the oxidation rate
431 decreased only slightly (*ca.* 0.3 min^{-1} for SG 700 °C/1 h@C and Co(II) ions).
432 Nevertheless, from the results obtained for PMS consumption, it's possible to assure
433 that the oxidant is being activated by Co(II) ions (compare the low chemical oxidation
434 ability of PMS in Fig. S17 and S18 - magenta circles).

435

436 3.3 UHPLC-QToF MS and carboxylic acid determinations: IMD degradation
437 byproducts and pathways

438

439 For the UHPLC-QToF MS experiments, only five intermediates were detected
440 when using the optimized conditions (0.125 g L^{-1} catalyst, $500 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ PMS and pH
441 7.0) for the SG 400 °C/1 h compound. The latter was chosen due to the similarities
442 observed among the assayed compounds (see Fig. 4 and S15). The extracted ion
443 chromatogram and tandem mass spectrometry (MS/MS) analyses of IMD and its
444 byproducts can be seen in Fig. S19 and S20, respectively. Fig. 6 shows the
445 intermediates and proposed degradation route, which is in agreement with that reported

446 by Bougin et al. [36]. More information regarding the retention time and main ionic
447 fragments as well as the proposed fragmentation route of the main intermediates can be
448 seen in Table S10 and Fig. S21. All oxidation steps occur on the imidazolidine ring,
449 mediated by HO• in consecutive oxidation steps, (see byproducts P3 and P4) or even
450 SO₄•⁻ radicals (followed by hydrolysis reaction for the latter) and to a less extent by
451 ¹O₂. Three intermediates (P1, P2, and P5) exhibited a rupture or loss of the
452 imidazolidine ring. All proposed chemical structures of intermediates agree with those
453 previously reported [36–39]. Although a low number of intermediates was detected, all
454 of them were organochlorine byproducts and persistent, mainly P2 and P1 as well as
455 IMD until 120 min of treatment, as showed in the extracted ion chromatograms of Fig.
456 S22. In the final stages of the oxidation process, only three carboxylic acids (see Fig.
457 S23) were detected at concentrations as low as 1 mg L⁻¹ and close to the quantification
458 limit. Inorganic ions resulting from IMD oxidation (*i.e.*, NO₃⁻ and Cl⁻) were not
459 detected by ion chromatography due to interferences in conductivity of the baseline
460 promoted by the PMS salt precursor.

461

462 3.4 Determination of the main working oxidants

463 To confirm the main produced byproducts resulting from DMPO oxidation by
464 HO• radicals, UHPLC-QToF MS measurements were carried out as described in Text
465 S3. An overview of the main detected DMPO byproducts can be seen upon analyses of
466 the total and extracted ion chromatograms of Fig. S24. Independently of the activation
467 agent (CoFe₂O₄ and Co(II) ions) used, the obtained profile and detected species were
468 the same and mainly due to HO• addition reactions or H abstractions (typically
469 promoted by HO• as the SO₄•⁻ radicals are predominant under acidic conditions
470 [40,41]), *i.e.*, DMPO/2OH, DMPO•/2OH, DMPO•/O, DMPO/OH, 2DMPO/-OH,
471 2DMPO/O-3H, 2DMPO/-H e DMPO/-3H. The MS/MS spectra of previous
472 intermediates is showed in Fig. S25. As expected and due to the low stability of DMPO-
473 SO₄ [42] and solution pH, no intermediates resulting from SO₄•⁻ addition reactions were
474 detected. The proposed fragmentation route of the main reported DMPO intermediate
475 species can be seen in Fig. S26, which agree with that previously reported [43]
476 considering the DMPO/OH, DMPO/2OH, DMPO•/2OH and DMPO•/O intermediates.
477 Electron spin resonance measurements were also performed to elucidate DMPO-OH
478 patterns, but they led to inconclusive results (see Fig. S27).

479 The scavenging experiments using isopropyl alcohol, tert-butyl alcohol, furfuryl
480 alcohol, and L-histidine can be seen in Fig. 7. As expected, IMD oxidation was
481 completely inhibited in the presence of isopropyl alcohol due to its prompt reaction with
482 HO^\bullet and $\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$ species [44]. However, when using t-butyl alcohol, commonly known as
483 a more selective scavenger for HO^\bullet radical than $\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$ [44], IMD was completely
484 oxidized. Clearly, that behavior suggests that HO^\bullet and $\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$ radicals participate in the
485 IMD oxidation. When analyzing the deleterious effects of furfuryl alcohol and L-
486 histidine on IMD oxidation, the role of $^1\text{O}_2$ is readily attested. To get further evidence
487 on the production of $^1\text{O}_2$ since controversy on the use of furfuryl alcohol exists [45],
488 experiments were carried out using ABDA, which is a specific compound to react with
489 $^1\text{O}_2$ [30] as can be seen in Fig. 8. For both tested processes, *i.e.* using CoFe_2O_4 and
490 Co(II) ions, the UV vis signal of ABDA was depleted after 5 min reaction with a
491 significant increase of dissolved oxygen (see Fig. S28). No side reactions between PMS
492 and ABDA were observed (see Fig. S29). Thus, considering the reported tests, IMD
493 oxidation by PMS activation using CoFe_2O_4 and Co(II) ions led to radical (HO^\bullet and
494 $\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$) and nonradical ($^1\text{O}_2$) species.

495

496 *3.5 Recycling test, time evolution changes of the CMF compound and proposed PMS*
497 *activation mechanism*

498 Five consecutive tests were carried out using the SG 400 °C/1 h compound in the
499 optimized conditions (0.125 g L^{-1} catalyst, $500 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ PMS and pH 7.0) as showed in
500 Fig. S30. As expected and due to leaching of Co(II) ions, the performance of the SG
501 400 °C/1 h compound was not altered during consecutive experiments.

502 To verify possible modifications on the crystalline integrity, surface chemical
503 groups, and charge transfer resistance of the CMF compounds, XRD, XPS and
504 electrochemical impedance measurements were carried out in all samples after their use
505 in the ISCO of IMD. The studied powders resulted from the experiments reported in
506 Fig. 4. As can be seen in Fig. S31 and S32, no structural changes were observed after
507 the ISCO of IMD. Concerning the XPS, used to analyze the evolution of near-surface
508 layer, no pronounced changes were observed as showed in the deconvoluted high-
509 resolution spectra of Fig. S33 to S36. To simplify the visualization of XPS results, the
510 evolution of the peak area percentage of the surface chemical states was compiled in bar
511 graphs and displayed in Fig. S37 to S39. The main differences observed between the as
512 prepared (AsP) and used (Us) samples are: *i*) appearance of K 2p peaks on the C 1s

513 spectra for the Cpt samples after their use, a contamination which comes from the PMS
 514 salt (K^+ ion source), *ii*) increase of hydroxyl groups, as observed in the O 1s, Co 2p_{3/2},
 515 and Fe 2p_{3/2} spectra, and decrease of the lattice oxygen (O 1s O-Metal peak at ~530 eV)
 516 observed for the SG samples due to the presence of oxygenated hydrocarbons, as
 517 reported in [25], and *iii*) evident decrease of Co(II) (~780 eV) and Fe(III) (~711 eV)
 518 species for both SG and Cpt samples, indicating the occurrence of leaching of these
 519 species. The Fe (II) component exhibited a distinct behavior, for the SG samples a
 520 reduction and Cpt an increase. The absence of IMD adsorption and its oxidized
 521 byproducts on the material's surface were also confirmed before and after testing by
 522 FTIR measurements (data not showed). The spectra showed no changes before and after
 523 the reaction, indicating that the initially absorbed IMD molecules were transferred into
 524 the solution.

525 Considering the obtained results on the role of Co(II) ions in the PMS activation
 526 and surface changes of the CMF compound, the following mechanism may take place:
 527 *i*) Co(II) species on the nanoparticle surface ($\equiv\text{Co(II)}$) are oxidized and leached (leaving
 528 an empty site $\equiv\square$) into the solution (Eq. 1) resulting in a homogeneous reaction (Eq. 2 –
 529 5) [46], and *ii*) Fe(III) is reduced to Fe(II) (Eq. 6) that is possibly leached into the
 530 solution (Eq. 7). As previously discussed, $^1\text{O}_2$ was detected and could be produced
 531 according to Eq. 8. At neutral solutions (pH 7), the produced $\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$ radical might be
 532 readily converted to HO^\bullet (Eq. 9), as detected during UHPLC-QToF MS measurements.

533

543

544 Li *et al.* [35] reported that Co(II) ions can complex with PMS leading to
 545 Co(II)–OOSO₃⁻ species (strongly pH dependent) prone to form Co(III) and $\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$
 546 radical (Eq. 10). The use of a phosphate buffer solution can also result in complexation

547 between PMS, Co(II), and H_2PO_4^- (L) ions forming L-Co(II)-OOSO_3^- of distinct
 548 reactivity [47]. However, in the present study, no differences in IMD oxidation were
 549 observed in the presence or absence of a buffered solution (except of increased PMS
 550 consumption) probably due to the amount of PMS used. The coupling between CMF
 551 and PMS was indirectly observed during OCP measurements carried out using
 552 electrodes made with distinctly prepared CMF nanoparticles (see Fig. S40). As can be
 553 apprehended from that figure, electrode potential increased continuously after PMS
 554 addition into solution (*i.e.* oxidation through surface modification), without
 555 interferences from IMD.

556

558

559 To access the evolution of the charge transfer resistance of the CMF oxide,
 560 electrochemical impedance measurements were carried out for the AsP and Us samples
 561 synthesized by the SG and Cpt methods. The results are shown in Fig. S41 to S44. The
 562 equivalent circuit used to obtain the best fits of the experimental data was composed of
 563 the solution resistance (R_{sol}), carbon support charge transfer resistance (R_{C}) in parallel
 564 with constant phase elements CPE_{C} , and the oxide charge transfer resistance (R_{oxide}) in
 565 parallel with CPE_{Oxide} . Among these parameters, the values of R_{oxide} before and after
 566 testing are shown in Fig. S45. An abrupt rise of the R_{oxide} values was observed after use
 567 for the SG 400 °C/1 h sample (the other Us values also increased but were not
 568 determined due to lack of fit quality). This behavior could be due to the increase of
 569 surface hydroxyl groups [48], which, however, did not affect the oxidation performance
 570 of the CMF since the IMD oxidation reaction through PMS activation proceeded by the
 571 leached Co(II) ions (eq. 2 and 5). Surface hydroxylation can occur on defects of the
 572 particle surface, specially at oxygen vacancies, that may lead to important surface
 573 reactions [49–51] or at metal sited (Eq. 11) as showed in the work of Lyu et al. [52].

574

576

577 4. Conclusions

578

579 Nanometric CoFe_2O_4 magnetic ferrite was successfully synthesized and
 580 characterized using the sol-gel and co-precipitation methods to activate

581 peroxymonosulfate (PMS) oxidant under neutral conditions. After optimization of the
582 catalyst load and PMS concentration, IMD oxidation rate and levels remained constant
583 showing a complete oxidation of IMD within 30 min independently of the preparation
584 procedure. Further experiments showed that this was due to Co(II) ion leaching from
585 the catalyst particles. Efforts to minimize ion leaching were unsuccessful since Co(II)
586 ion concentrations as low as $20 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ were sufficient to activate PMS by the
587 Co(II)/Co(III) redox couple in the presence or absence of a phosphate buffer at pH 7.
588 Future studies should therefore double check the effect of ion leaching from any solid
589 oxide catalyst to distinguish the role or contribution of homogeneous and heterogeneous
590 reactions. In addition, pH monitoring and correction should be mandatory as well as the
591 relationship between buffer (if used) and PMS oxidant.

592 PMS activation by CoFe_2O_4 and/or Co(II) ions led to the production of radical
593 (HO^\bullet and $\text{SO}_4^{\bullet-}$) and nonradical ($^1\text{O}_2$) as detected and confirmed through UHPLC-
594 QToF MS measurements using DMPO as spin probe and scavenging experiments,
595 particularly 9,10-anthracenediyl-bis(methylene)dimalonic acid for $^1\text{O}_2$. The latter led to
596 high oxidation levels even in a complex water matrix such as simulated municipal
597 wastewater Concerning the oxidation byproducts of IMD, only five intermediates
598 derived from hydroxylation addition reactions on the imidazolidine aromatic ring were
599 detected as well as short chain carboxylic acids. Considering the structural and
600 electrochemical analysis carried out on the assayed CoFe_2O_4 samples, no significant
601 changes were observed except for a decrease of Co(II) and Fe(III) phases and an
602 increase of the oxide charge transfer resistance. These findings confirm the unique role
603 of CoFe_2O_4 nanoparticles as efficient Co(II) ion source.

604

605 **Acknowledgements**

606

607 Financial support and scholarships from the Brazilian funding agencies: São Paulo
608 Research Foundation – FAPESP (#2014/50918-7, #2019/07943-4, and #2021/13604-8),
609 National Council for Scientific and Technological Development – CNPq
610 (#465357/2014-8, #305943/2020-0, #406537/2021-6, and #307800/2021-0),
611 Coordination of Superior Level Staff Improvement – Capes (Finance Code 001), and
612 Finep (Financiadora de Estudos e Projetos, grant number #01.22.0179.00, MARTMA)
613 are gratefully acknowledged. The authors also thank the Laboratory of Structural

614 Characterization (LCE/DEMa/UFSCar) and LNNano/CNPEM for the general facilities
615 and use of XPS (proposals #XPS-20221506 and #XPS-20230048).

616

617 **References**

618

- 619 [1] J.A.P. Silva, G.G. Lima, C.F. Camilo-Cotrim, E.F.L.C. Bailão, S.S. Caramori, J.C.
620 Nabout, L.M. Almeida, Impact of e-waste toxicity on health and nature: trends,
621 biases, and future directions, *Water. Air. Soil Pollut.* 234 (2023) 320.
622 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11270-023-06328-2>.
- 623 [2] S. Aslam, A. Khurram, R. Hussain, A. Qadir, S.R. Ahmad, Sources, distribution,
624 and incipient threats of polymeric microplastic released from food storage plastic
625 materials, *Environ. Monit. Assess.* 195 (2023) 638.
626 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-023-11242-5>.
- 627 [3] H. Xie, X. Tian, X. Lin, R. Chen, S. Hameed, L. Wang, Y.-L. Yu, B. Li, Y.-F. Li,
628 Nanoplastic-induced biological effects in vivo and in vitro: an overview, *Rev.*
629 *Environ. Contam. Toxicol.* 261 (2023) 2. [https://doi.org/10.1007/s44169-023-](https://doi.org/10.1007/s44169-023-00027-z)
630 [00027-z](https://doi.org/10.1007/s44169-023-00027-z).
- 631 [4] L. Najam, T. Alam, Occurrence, distribution, and fate of emerging persistent
632 organic pollutants (POPs) in the environment, in: T. Aftab (Ed.), *Emerg. Contam.*
633 *Plants*, Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2023: pp. 135–161.
634 https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-22269-6_6.
- 635 [5] S.D. Warner, D. Bekele, C.P. Nathanail, S. Chadalavada, R. Naidu,
636 Climate-influenced hydrobiogeochemistry and groundwater remedy design: A
637 review, *Remediat. J.* (2023) rem.21753. <https://doi.org/10.1002/rem.21753>.
- 638 [6] A.K.S. Pereira, L.F. Silva, G.A.F. Barbosa, T.G. Miranda, R.R. Sousa, R.A.
639 Sarmiento, N.L.G.D. Souza, D.H. Pereira, G.S. Cavallini, The socio-environmental
640 and human health problems related to the use of pesticides and the use of advanced
641 oxidative processes for their degradation: Brazil, *Water.* 15 (2023) 1608.
642 <https://doi.org/10.3390/w15081608>.
- 643 [7] N. Gaur, D. Dutta, A. Singh, R. Dubey, D.V. Kamboj, Recent advances in the
644 elimination of persistent organic pollutants by photocatalysis, *Front. Environ. Sci.*
645 10 (2022) 872514. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2022.872514>.
- 646 [8] S. Boulkhessaim, A. Gacem, S.H. Khan, A. Amari, V.K. Yadav, H.N. Harharah,
647 A.M. Elkhaleefa, K.K. Yadav, S. Rather, H.-J. Ahn, B.-H. Jeon, Emerging trends
648 in the remediation of persistent organic pollutants using nanomaterials and related
649 processes: a review, *Nanomaterials.* 12 (2022) 2148.
650 <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano12132148>.
- 651 [9] M.F. Hanafi, N. Sapawe, A review on the current techniques and technologies of
652 organic pollutants removal from water/wastewater, *Mater. Today Proc.* 31 (2020)
653 A158–A165. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2021.01.265>.
- 654 [10] J. Lee, U. von Gunten, J.-H. Kim, Persulfate-based advanced oxidation: critical
655 assessment of opportunities and roadblocks, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 54 (2020)
656 3064–3081. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.9b07082>.
- 657 [11] S. Wang, Y. Zhang, Zero valent iron-electro-Fenton-peroxymonosulfate (ZVI-E-
658 Fenton-PMS) process for industrial wastewater treatment, *RSC Adv.* 13 (2023)
659 15063–15076. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D2RA06653J>.

- 660 [12] I.A. Ike, K.G. Linden, J.D. Orbell, M. Duke, Critical review of the science and
661 sustainability of persulphate advanced oxidation processes, *Chem. Eng. J.* 338
662 (2018) 651–669. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2018.01.034>.
- 663 [13] B. Wang, Y. Wang, A comprehensive review on persulfate activation treatment of
664 wastewater, *Sci. Total Environ.* 831 (2022) 154906.
665 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.154906>.
- 666 [14] D.B. Miklos, C. Remy, M. Jekel, K.G. Linden, J.E. Drewes, U. Hübner,
667 Evaluation of advanced oxidation processes for water and wastewater treatment –
668 a critical review, *Water Res.* 139 (2018) 118–131.
669 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.watres.2018.03.042>.
- 670 [15] X. Wu, J.-H. Kim, Outlook on single atom catalysts for persulfate-based advanced
671 oxidation, *ACS EST Eng.* 2 (2022) 1776–1796.
672 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsestengg.2c00187>.
- 673 [16] Y. Ding, C. Pan, X. Peng, Q. Mao, Y. Xiao, L. Fu, J. Huang, Deep mineralization
674 of bisphenol A by catalytic peroxymonosulfate activation with nano CuO/Fe₃O₄
675 with strong Cu-Fe interaction, *Chem. Eng. J.* 384 (2020) 123378.
676 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2019.123378>.
- 677 [17] L. Chen, X. Zuo, L. Zhou, Y. Huang, S. Yang, T. Cai, D. Ding, Efficient
678 heterogeneous activation of peroxymonosulfate by facilely prepared Co/Fe
679 bimetallic oxides: kinetics and mechanism, *Chem. Eng. J.* 345 (2018) 364–374.
680 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2018.03.169>.
- 681 [18] G.P. Anipsitakis, D.D. Dionysiou, Radical generation by the interaction of
682 transition metals with common oxidants, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 38 (2004) 3705–
683 3712. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es035121o>.
- 684 [19] Y. Zhou, Y. Zhang, X. Hu, Synergistic coupling Co₃Fe₇ alloy and CoFe₂O₄ spinel
685 for highly efficient removal of 2,4-dichlorophenol by activating
686 peroxymonosulfate, *Chemosphere.* 242 (2020) 125244.
687 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2019.125244>.
- 688 [20] Y. Li, W. Zhu, Q. Guo, X. Wang, L. Zhang, X. Gao, Y. Luo, Highly efficient
689 degradation of sulfamethoxazole (SMX) by activating peroxymonosulfate (PMS)
690 with CoFe₂O₄ in a wide pH range, *Sep. Purif. Technol.* 276 (2021) 119403.
691 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2021.119403>.
- 692 [21] L. Wang, H. Xu, N. Jiang, Z. Wang, J. Jiang, T. Zhang, Trace cupric species
693 triggered decomposition of peroxymonosulfate and degradation of organic
694 pollutants: Cu(III) being the primary and selective intermediate oxidant, *Environ.*
695 *Sci. Technol.* 54 (2020) 4686–4694. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.0c00284>.
- 696 [22] B. Liu, W. Song, H. Wu, Y. Xu, Y. Sun, Y. Yu, H. Zheng, S. Wan, Enhanced
697 oxidative degradation of norfloxacin using peroxymonosulfate activated by oily
698 sludge carbon-based nanoparticles CoFe₂O₄/OSC, *Chem. Eng. J.* 400 (2020)
699 125947. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2020.125947>.
- 700 [23] J. Xu, Z. Zhang, J. Hong, D. Wang, G. Fan, J. Zhou, Y. Wang, Co-doped Fe₃O₄/α-
701 FeOOH for highly efficient peroxymonosulfate activation to degrade
702 trimethoprim: occurrence of hybrid non-radical and radical pathways, *J. Env.*
703 *Manage.* 325 (2023) 116459. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.116459>.
- 704 [24] M. Xu, J. Li, Y. Yan, X. Zhao, J. Yan, Y. Zhang, B. Lai, X. Chen, L. Song,
705 Catalytic degradation of sulfamethoxazole through peroxymonosulfate activated
706 with expanded graphite loaded CoFe₂O₄ particles, *Chem. Eng. J.* 369 (2019) 403–
707 413. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2019.03.075>.
- 708 [25] X. Li, Z. Liu, Y. Zhu, L. Song, Z. Dong, S. Niu, C. Lyu, Facile synthesis and
709 synergistic mechanism of CoFe₂O₄@three-dimensional graphene aerogels towards

- 710 peroxymonosulfate activation for highly efficient degradation of recalcitrant
711 organic pollutants, *Sci. Total Environ.* 749 (2020) 141466.
712 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.141466>.
- 713 [26] K. Srinivasa Rao, S.V. Ranga Nayakulu, M. Chaitanya Varma, G.S.V.R.K.
714 Choudary, K.H. Rao, Controlled phase evolution and the occurrence of single
715 domain CoFe_2O_4 nanoparticles synthesized by PVA assisted sol-gel method, *J.*
716 *Magn. Magn. Mater.* 451 (2018) 602–608.
717 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmmm.2017.11.069>.
- 718 [27] M. Basak, Md.L. Rahman, Md.F. Ahmed, B. Biswas, N. Sharmin, Calcination
719 effect on structural, morphological and magnetic properties of nano-sized CoFe_2O_4
720 developed by a simple co-precipitation technique, *Mater. Chem. Phys.* 264 (2021)
721 124442. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matchemphys.2021.124442>.
- 722 [28] X. Li, Z. Zhao, H. Li, J. Qian, Degradation of organic contaminants in the
723 CoFe_2O_4 /peroxymonosulfate process: The overlooked role of Co(II) -PMS
724 complex, *Chem. Eng. J. Adv.* 8 (2021) 100143.
725 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceja.2021.100143>.
- 726 [29] C. Liang, C.-F. Huang, N. Mohanty, R.M. Kurakalva, A rapid spectrophotometric
727 determination of persulfate anion in ISCO, *Chemosphere.* 73 (2008) 1540–1543.
728 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2008.08.043>.
- 729 [30] T. Entradas, S. Waldron, M. Volk, The detection sensitivity of commonly used
730 singlet oxygen probes in aqueous environments, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. B.* 204
731 (2020) 111787. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jphotobiol.2020.111787>.
- 732 [31] C. Powell, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy database XPS, Version 4.1, NIST
733 standard reference database 20, (1989). <https://doi.org/10.18434/T4T88K>.
- 734 [32] W. Najjar, S. Azabou, S. Sayadi, A. Ghorbel, Catalytic wet peroxide photo-
735 oxidation of phenolic olive oil mill wastewater contaminants, *Appl. Catal. B*
736 *Environ.* 74 (2007) 11–18. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apcatb.2007.01.007>.
- 737 [33] T. Zhang, H. Zhu, J.-P. Croué, Production of Sulfate Radical from
738 Peroxymonosulfate Induced by a Magnetically Separable CuFe_2O_4 Spinel in
739 Water: Efficiency, Stability, and Mechanism, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 47 (2013)
740 2784–2791. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es304721g>.
- 741 [34] P. Hu, M. Long, Cobalt-catalyzed sulfate radical-based advanced oxidation: a
742 review on heterogeneous catalysts and applications, *Appl. Catal. B Environ.* 181
743 (2016) 103–117. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apcatb.2015.07.024>.
- 744 [35] H. Li, Z. Zhao, J. Qian, B. Pan, Are free radicals the primary reactive species in
745 Co(II) -mediated activation of peroxymonosulfate? New evidence for the role of
746 the Co(II) -peroxymonosulfate complex, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 55 (2021) 6397–
747 6406. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.1c02015>.
- 748 [36] M. Bourgin, F. Violleau, L. Debrauwer, J. Albet, Ozonation of imidacloprid in
749 aqueous solutions: reaction monitoring and identification of degradation products,
750 *J. Hazard. Mater.* 190 (2011) 60–68.
751 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2011.02.065>.
- 752 [37] B.S. Baghirzade, U. Yetis, F.B. Dilek, Imidacloprid elimination by O_3 and O_3/UV :
753 kinetics study, matrix effect, and mechanism insight, *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* 28
754 (2021) 24535–24551. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-020-09355-2>.
- 755 [38] J. Li, Y. Jiang, D. Li, Determination of imidacloprid and its relevant metabolites in
756 tomato using modified QuEChERS combined with ultrahigh-pressure liquid
757 chromatography/Orbitrap tandem mass spectrometry, *J. Sci. Food Agric.* 99 (2019)
758 5211–5218. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jsfa.9769>.

- 759 [39] X. Cui, X. Liu, C. Lin, M. He, W. Ouyang, Activation of peroxymonosulfate using
760 drinking water treatment residuals modified by hydrothermal treatment for
761 imidacloprid degradation, *Chemosphere*. 254 (2020) 126820.
762 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2020.126820>.
- 763 [40] X. Li, B. Jie, H. Lin, Z. Deng, J. Qian, Y. Yang, X. Zhang, Application of sulfate
764 radicals-based advanced oxidation technology in degradation of trace organic
765 contaminants (TrOCs): Recent advances and prospects, *J. Environ. Manage.* 308
766 (2022) 114664. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.114664>.
- 767 [41] M. Ahmadi, F. Ghanbari, M. Moradi, Photocatalysis assisted by
768 peroxymonosulfate and persulfate for benzotriazole degradation: effect of pH on
769 sulfate and hydroxyl radicals, *Water Sci Technol.* 72 (2015) 2095–2102.
770 <https://doi.org/10.2166/wst.2015.437>.
- 771 [42] W.-D. Oh, Z. Dong, T.-T. Lim, Generation of sulfate radical through
772 heterogeneous catalysis for organic contaminants removal: Current development,
773 challenges and prospects, *Appl. Catal. B Environ.* 194 (2016) 169–201.
774 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apcatb.2016.04.003>.
- 775 [43] Y. Núñez-de la Rosa, L.G.C. Durango, M.R. Forim, O.R. Nascimento, P. Hammer,
776 J.M. Aquino, Unraveling the time evolution and post mortem changes of
777 nanometric MnOOH during in situ oxidation of ciprofloxacin by activated
778 peroxymonosulfate, *Appl. Catal. B Environ.* 327 (2023) 122439.
779 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apcatb.2023.122439>.
- 780 [44] C. Liang, H.-W. Su, Identification of sulfate and hydroxyl radicals in thermally
781 activated persulfate, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 48 (2009) 5558–5562.
782 <https://doi.org/10.1021/ie9002848>.
- 783 [45] Y. Yang, G. Banerjee, G.W. Brudvig, J.-H. Kim, J.J. Pignatello, Oxidation of
784 organic compounds in water by unactivated peroxymonosulfate, *Environ. Sci.
785 Technol.* 52 (2018) 5911–5919. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.8b00735>.
- 786 [46] G.P. Anipsitakis, D.D. Dionysiou, Degradation of organic contaminants in water
787 with sulfate radicals generated by the conjunction of peroxymonosulfate with
788 cobalt, *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 37 (2003) 4790–4797.
789 <https://doi.org/10.1021/es0263792>.
- 790 [47] Y.R. Goo, A.C. Maity, K.-B. Cho, Y.-M. Lee, M.S. Seo, Y.J. Park, J. Cho, W.
791 Nam, Tuning the reactivity of chromium(III)-superoxo species by coordinating
792 axial ligands, *Inorg. Chem.* 54 (2015) 10513–10520.
793 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.inorgchem.5b02068>.
- 794 [48] T.T. Pinto, Y. Núñez-de la Rosa, P. Hammer, J.M. Aquino, On the performance of
795 self-organized TiO₂ nanotubes@MnO_x as supercapacitor: Influence of the heat
796 treatment, cathodic treatment, water aging, and thermal oxides, *Electrochimica
797 Acta.* 408 (2022) 139898. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2022.139898>.
- 798 [49] Y. Zhong, R. Wang, J. Chen, C. Duan, Z. Huang, S. Yu, H. Guo, Y. Zhou,
799 Surface-terminated hydroxyl groups for deciphering the facet-dependent
800 photocatalysis of anatase TiO₂, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces.* 14 (2022) 17601–
801 17609. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.2c04302>.
- 802 [50] X. Zhao, J. Wang, L. Lian, G. Zhang, P. An, K. Zeng, H. He, T. Yuan, J. Huang,
803 L. Wang, Y.-N. Liu, Oxygen vacancy-reinforced water-assisted proton hopping for
804 enhanced catalytic hydrogenation, *ACS Catal.* 13 (2023) 2326–2334.
805 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acscatal.2c05376>.
- 806 [51] L. Meng, D. Rao, W. Tian, F. Cao, X. Yan, L. Li, Simultaneous manipulation of
807 O-doping and metal vacancy in atomically thin Zn₁₀In₁₆S₃₄ nanosheet arrays

- 808 toward improved photoelectrochemical performance, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 57
809 (2018) 16882–16887. <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.201811632>.
- 810 [52] C. Lyu, L. Zhang, D. He, B. Su, Y. Lyu, Micrometer-sized NiOOH hierarchical
811 spheres for enhanced degradation of sulfadiazine via synergistic adsorption and
812 catalytic oxidation in peroxymonosulfate system, *Chin. Chem. Lett.* 33 (2022)
813 930–934. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ccllet.2021.07.012>.
- 814
- 815

FIGURE CAPTIONS

816

817

818 **Fig. 1** – Transmission electron microscope (TEM) images of the CoFe_2O_4 magnetic
819 ferrite (CMF) nanoparticles prepared by the Sol-gel (a and b) and Co-precipitation (c
820 and d) methods and thermally treated at 400 °C (a and c) and 700 °C (b and d).

821

822 **Fig. 2 a)** Remaining fraction of IMD (IMD fraction) and **b)** PMS consumption as a
823 function of treatment time (t) using distinct amounts of CoFe_2O_4 (obtained by the SG
824 method and thermally treated at 400 °C for 1 h – SG 400 °C/1 h). **Conditions:** 500 μmol
825 L^{-1} PMS, pH 7.0, 10 mmol L^{-1} KH_2PO_4 , 150 mL of treating solution with 50 mg L^{-1}
826 IMD at 25 °C. Error bars refer to two repetitions, except for the oxidant consumption.
827 All experiments were carried out in the dark. w/o = without.

828

829 **Fig. 3 a)** Remaining fraction of IMD (IMD fraction) and **b)** PMS consumption as a
830 function of treatment time (t) using distinct concentration of PMS (see inset).
831 **Conditions:** 0.125 g L^{-1} CMF (SG 400°C/1 h sample), pH 7.0, 10 mmol L^{-1} KH_2PO_4 ,
832 150 mL of treating solution with 50 mg L^{-1} IMD at 25 °C. Error bars refer to two
833 repetitions, except for the oxidant consumption. All experiments were carried out in the
834 dark.

835

836 **Fig. 4 a)** Remaining fraction of IMD (IMD fraction) and **b)** PMS consumption as a
837 function of treatment time (t) using CMF (cobalt magnetic ferrite) catalysts prepared at
838 different conditions (see inset). **Conditions:** 0.125 g L^{-1} CMF, 500 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ PMS, pH
839 7.0, 10 mmol L^{-1} KH_2PO_4 , 150 mL of treating solution with 50 mg L^{-1} IMD at 25 °C.
840 Error bars refer to two repetitions, except for the oxidant consumption. All experiments
841 were carried out in the dark.

842

843 **Fig. 5** Remaining fraction of IMD (IMD fraction) and **b)** PMS consumption as a
844 function of treatment time (t) using distinct concentration values of Co(II) and Fe(III)
845 ions (see inset). **Conditions:** 0.125 g L^{-1} CMF, 500 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ PMS, pH 7.0, 10 mmol L^{-1}
846 KH_2PO_4 , 150 mL of treating solution with 50 mg L^{-1} IMD at 25 °C. Error bars refer to
847 two repetitions, except for the oxidant consumption. All experiments were carried out in
848 the dark.

849

850 **Fig. 6** Proposed degradation pathways of IMD using the SG 400 °C/1 h compound to
851 the *in situ* chemical activation of PMS. **Conditions:** 0.125 g L⁻¹ CMF, 500 μmol L⁻¹
852 PMS, pH 7.0, 10 mmol L⁻¹ KH₂PO₄, 150 mL of treating solution with 50 mg L⁻¹ IMD
853 at 25 °C.

854

855 **Fig. 7** Remaining fraction of IMD (IMD fraction) as a function of treatment time (*t*)
856 using distinct compounds (isopropyl alcohol, t-butyl alcohol, furfuryl alcohol, and L-
857 histidine) as scavengers. **Conditions:** 0.125 g L⁻¹ CMF (SG 400 °C/1 h), 500 μmol L⁻¹
858 PMS, pH 7.0, 10 mmol L⁻¹ KH₂PO₄, 150 mL of treating solution with 50 mg L⁻¹ IMD
859 at 25 °C.

860

861 **Fig. 8** Evolution of UV vis spectra for the 9,10-anthracenediyl-bis(methylene)dimalonic
862 acid (ABDA) compound using the CMF compound (in the a) presence and b) absence
863 of methanol) and Co(II) ions (in the c) presence and d) absence of methanol) to activate
864 peroxy monosulfate without imidacloprid. e) the specific reaction between ABDA and
865 ¹O₂. **Conditions:** 0.125 g L⁻¹ CMF (SG 400 °C/1 h) or 200 μg L⁻¹ of Co(II) ions in the
866 presence of PMS (500 μmol L⁻¹) at pH ~7 and without buffer - see Text S4 in the
867 supplementary material file for further details.